

Short Paper: IoT Applications in Viticulture: A Case Study on Sensor Network and Data-Driven Vineyard Management

1st Simona Stojanova
*Faculty of Electrical Engineering
University of Ljubljana*
Ljubljana, Slovenia
simona.stojanova@fe.uni-lj.si

2nd Emilija Stojmenova Duh
*Faculty of Electrical Engineering
University of Ljubljana*
Ljubljana, Slovenia
emilija.stojmenova@fe.uni-lj.si

3rd Andrej Kos
*Faculty of Electrical Engineering
University of Ljubljana*
Ljubljana, Slovenia
andrej.kos@fe.uni-lj.si

4th Mojca Volk
*Faculty of Electrical Engineering
University of Ljubljana*
Ljubljana, Slovenia
mojca.volk@fe.uni-lj.si

Nowadays the agricultural sector is heavily impacted by climate change. Consequently, the concept of sustainable agriculture is gaining traction, focusing not only on economic gain but also on preserving natural and human resources, thus addressing all three pillars of sustainability: economic, environmental, and social. The purpose of this paper is to present IoT sensors installed at a pilot demo vineyard, with the aim of achieving precision viticulture based on real time data collection and informed decision making. This helps farmers make informed decisions regarding the necessity, location and timing of treatments, such as an application of phytopharmaceuticals spraying. IoT sensor infrastructure is important for rural business entities as it influences their environmental, economic, and social aspects, improving farms profitability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Continuous technological advancements bring new opportunities for innovative ideas, making sustainable development increasingly reliant on digitalization. The use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in different fields of rural areas is crucial for rural development, especially in agriculture, which is seen as the main economic activity and thus the most important sector in rural areas [1]. Most businesses operating in this sector are local, small, and mid-sized enterprises (SMEs), which is an important aspect as they are said to be the backbone of the European economy [2].

However, climate change is threatening agricultural production and food security. As a result, the concept of sustainable agriculture is gaining importance, focusing on the general principle of sustainable development that “we must meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” [3]. Accordingly, the focus is not only on the economic gain, but also the natural and human resources, covering all three pillars of sustainability [4].

II. SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

Sustainable agriculture can be achieved through technology utilization. Access to technology in rural areas is limited and there is a lack of digital competences yet highlighted as extremely important for the development of underserved communities [5]. Moreover, the adoption of ICT in agriculture does not always mean higher profits for every farmer and entity. The key issues in sustainable agriculture are on one hand higher yields and on the other hand resource utilization, such as land and water [6], which is commonly referred to as precision agriculture. There are also other barriers associated with implementing ICT technologies in agriculture, such as financial barriers, digital literacy of the farmers, data management, availability of telecommunication infrastructure and most importantly nowadays - lack of integration between the systems, meaning that there is a need for connecting and integrating different ICT tools into one integrated solution. Farmers need integrated and customized solutions that can support them through different steps of the production process with the goal of achieving production optimization, cost-effectiveness, better risk management and data-driven decisions with higher accuracy.

III. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES IN PRECISION AGRICULTURE

Precision Agriculture uses a variety of sensing technologies, including Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, to track the growth and health of crops in different stages. IoT seems to be a significant revolution for the next generation, with a crucial role in various sectors. It refers to a network of physical devices, vehicles, home appliances, and other electronics equipped with software, sensors, and actuators that can communicate and share data. IoT enables remote monitoring and control of these objects within existing infrastructures, facilitating greater integration between the physical world and digital systems. This integration leads to enhanced efficiency, accuracy, and economic benefits.

IoT's backbone is the sensors and actuators that allow for remote connectivity. The technology spans diverse applications, including smart grids, smart homes, intelligent transportation, and smart cities [7]. Different communication protocols such as 6LoWPAN, ZigBee, Bluetooth, RFID, Wi-Fi LoRaWaAN (used in this case study) are employed for precision agriculture. This technology involves collecting and processing vast amounts of data related to crop conditions. A range of factors, such as water availability, temperature, and other key parameters, play a role in plant health. Precision agriculture allows farmers to understand exactly what the crops need, where these needs are greatest, and how much is required at any given time. To gather this information, data is sourced from different parts of the field, including soil composition, the presence of pests and weeds, plant chlorophyll levels, and even local weather conditions. This data is analyzed to create agronomic recommendations. It's crucial that this detailed agronomic information is delivered to farmers promptly, allowing them to act on the recommendations and improve crop yields. Ultimately, precision agriculture helps farmers make informed decisions to ensure healthy crops and maximize productivity [8].

Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a crucial role as part of the IoT and decision support systems for sustainable agriculture due to its capacity to process vast quantities of data, derive valuable insights, and assist farmers in comprehending agricultural strategies and making precise evaluations [9]. AI has already led to numerous applications in precision agriculture. Researchers have integrated different AI methods to analyze large volumes of data from a variety of sources, such as satellite images and sensors, to predict crop health, detect disease outbreaks, identify potential threats, and forecast yield through image analysis and predictive modeling. This predictive capacity facilitates early intervention, which helps reduce crop losses, resource utilization and enhances productivity [10].

IV. CASE STUDY: VITICULTURE MONITORING SYSTEM

We present a viticulture case study that takes place within the Living Lab Smart Villages Network from Slovenia. It spans three regions in Slovenia, linking the east and west of the country, bringing together farmers, researchers, technology providers, and government representatives to cultivate a 'learning culture' through collaborative projects. IoT solutions for viticulture have been monitored and tested, addressing challenges related to sensor infrastructure, communication technology, data collection and processing, and user interface [11]. The Living Lab focuses on utilizing digital technology in viticulture to impact environmental, economic, and social sustainability. Main objectives of the LL include: 1. environmental: reducing water and pesticide usage in winegrowing, lowering CO₂ emissions, minimizing vineyard treatments; 2. social: promoting sustainable

business and time management practices; 3. economic: enhancing farm profitability.

The main challenges for Slovenian winemakers come from the poor communication coverage in rural areas and rugged terrain, which creates varying microclimates within the same vineyard. These factors impact the farm's profitability and have environmental and social implications. Monitoring rainfall, soil moisture and leaf wetness are important parameters that influence infections in the vineyard, which is one of the most common problems for this demo farm. To address this, winemakers need a dispersed network of sensors rather than a single weather station, to collect data throughout the whole vineyard. This setup is essential for accurately understanding vineyard conditions and making informed decisions, especially for organic farms. Within the currently ongoing project Codecs [12] we tested a new solution that had been in development for several years. The project goal is to enhance the collective ability to understand, evaluate, and anticipate the benefits and costs associated with farm digitalization. Whiting the project, we have identified a demo farm, Doppler Winery, a family- owned winery located in the Drava region of Slovenia, where the new technology is being tested. Due to their rugged terrain, the vineyard climate varies significantly across different areas, necessitating diverse responses, whereas standard IoT weather stations placed in a single location is unsuitable. The main goals for this demo farm are controlling water and substance use in winegrowing, reducing CO₂ emissions through fewer vineyard treatments, achieving time efficiency, and improving farm profitability. The main objective is to reduce the number of vineyard treatments by utilizing IoT support. The farm is transitioning to organic farming, requiring organic sprays to be applied to the vines promptly after a certain amount of rainfall. Thus, accurate rainfall data at specific micro-locations is crucial. The farm is experiencing significant climate change, which compels them to adapt. Consequently, they need more knowledge, information, and data. As a response, the technological solution implemented at this demo farm consists of a vineyard monitoring system, including IoT sensor infrastructure, positioned at different heights and locations. They collect viticultural data, including soil moisture, leaf wetness, and rainfall, in order to monitor microclimates in various parts of the vineyards.

Fig. 1. IoT Sensors for soil moisture, leaf wetness and rainfall.

The sensors are powered by standard AAA batteries and can operate for up to 10 years before needing a battery replacement [13]. With an average range of 15 km, these sensors communicate with a gateway located on the top of a hill using LoRaWAN technology. This connectivity was chosen due to its low energy consumption, long range, and easy configuration. It incurs no additional costs and allows for a privately managed network. The communication architecture involves devices sending data to the LoRaWAN gateway, which then transmits the data to the server and platforms. The gateway needs to be connected to an Ethernet or Wi-Fi network in order to be able to transmit the data. The data collection model is implemented on the ThingsBoard platform, where sensor data is stored and accessible via an application programming interface (API). ThingsBoard is an open-source platform for device management, data collection, visualization, and processing.

Using rule nodes in a rule engine, processed data trigger alarms to support vineyard management processes. Based on this data, the farmer can determine the optimal type and amount of treatment for a specific location within a vineyard and can properly act in case of an emergency. Technology provides real-time data on vineyard conditions, revealing that higher, well-aerated vineyards with less moisture face a lower infection risk than lower vineyards. These parameters are monitored daily, and based on the collected insights, there is a proper planning of vineyard activities and treatments only when and where needed. This data-driven approach ensures precise management and effective emergency responses in the vineyard. Collected data represents an important baseline for the introduction of AI that can support more advanced analytics, trending and predictions, which in turn can provide even more precise decision support.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, rural entities can contribute towards sustainable agricultural development by leveraging the use of smart data applications for resource efficiency and biodiversity protection, thus enhancing residents' quality of life and promoting social equality. The use case study demonstrates the significant potential of IoT technology in enhancing viticulture. Implementing a dispersed IoT sensor network and LoRaWAN communications infrastructure has enabled precise monitoring of vineyard conditions, leading to more informed decision-making. This approach has been shown to improve the efficiency of water and substance use, reduce CO₂ emissions, save time, and increase the farm's profitability. Provided example underscores the value of digital transformation in agriculture, offering a sustainable model that can be replicated in other regions to address environmental, economic, and social challenges in farming.

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